

IN MEDICINE FROM ECHOPHRAPHY USE

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Annotation

" Echophraphy " medicine in the field initial physical structures more explanation , analysis to do , to treat development , surgery and another in the fields used research and treatment methods in search of is used . Echophraphy , mainly , tuberculosis , different infectious diseases and traumas with depends organs and physical structures in determining used. Of exophraphy different different methods there is from them _ use to problems against coming circumstances determination and his instead of coming tools designation for application can _ Echophraphy results based on doctors , science development , hospitals _ and treatment laboratories convenience with working diagnosis tools as is used .

Key words : Echography , infasiv diagnostics, X-ray rays _

Introduction

Echophraphy in medicine all in the fields use can _ This method the following examples with explanation can _ Echophraphy , organ and physical structures study for x-ray rays and ultrasounds using organize will be done . Tuberculosis diseases X-ray , x-ray and computer tomography through in determining help give take can _ Echophraphy physical structures determination and treatment processes it is also used in explanation . Information get for tomography and x-ray results using doctor changes one different to do , radiation treatment to manage instruction preparations It is possible. Echophraphy , mainly , is high good quality x-ray rays and of ultrasounds high good quality members with done is increased . This method application , to doctors another diagnostic from tools received data about more information give , right choose and treatment processes in defining help give takes. Echophraphy in medicine practice take to go one diagnostic is a method and own into special advantages , but one how many harmful there are also sides . X-ray , x-ray radiation uses , and long term or a lot times in application this radiation is harmful . In particular , pregnant Women and children for of echophraphy very a lot application recommendation not done . Echophraphy , different organ and structures about common information shows , but some cases more briefly to be can _ Echophraphy tomography and x-ray pictures to

study able to be it is possible as a result diagnostic error and wrong to information take coming can _ Echography right to be done for right in doses radiation application necessary. Of exography damages reduce for , this method to use decision did from doctors own his opinion asking get very important _ Always diagnostic _ _ methods from use first doctor with consultation and his advice to hear need _

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Echography in medicine diagnosis in putting and treatment processes in defining one how many useful to the parties have to be can _ Echography , organ and physical structures about data in showing is used . These are diseases , changes or requiring treatment _ cases used. Echography , unnecessary radiation level uses , including x-ray radiation very a lot get can _ In this case , radiation level negative effect show for is reduced. Echography , diagnosis good show for organs and structures private indicators through good analysis does _ Echography , other radiological methods with compared to , small radiation level have will be This is pregnant women , children and many medicine in the fields of echography advantages shows. Echography all medicine in the fields does not apply , but one how many conditions , diseases detection , medical treatment and treatment development , surgery processes manage and another goals for very efficient to be can _ Choose in processes and treatment in the plan of echography useful sides doctors with advice as well as another _ diagnostic methods with to compare chance to be given and this method in management radiation level reduce very important _ Echography in medicine wide applied one diagnostic is a method and of medicine one how many in the fields important have _

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

X-ray rays , surroundings in the environment high to energy have is , of objects structure and material types difference to do chance will give . X-ray light in use around detectors and private tools , for example , X-ray film or sensors used. Detectors , roentgen rays through sent energy again working tools using , of objects mistakes determination for is used . Projectors while from the detectors received information describe for is used . They are roentgen rays to objects redirection , and _ as a result , lit of the object image harvest in doing help will give .

Conclusion .

Electrography of the object electricity actions and potentials in learning electricity from charges uses _ Electrography in methods , of objects

electricity right transmissions (EEG), myocardium electricity activity (ECG) and another electricity processes in learning is used . Electrography information get and especially spreadable in storage _ electricity signal get analog for and digital devices is used . These devices , processes get , process to give and analysis to do for is used . Electrography information a lot series computers and special programs through analysis does _ These programs are electric signal management , description and information more precisely reading for used. Electrography methods , medicine , neurology , cardiology and another fields according to diseases diagnosis to do and in treatment big role plays _ They are in medicine main diagnostic tools as is used and to doctors help will give . Epilepsy in cases , neurologists to EEG analysis based on crises and their properties explains . EMG analysis showing nerves (polyneuritis) and their _ properties in explanation important role plays Electrocardiography , heart the rhythm analysis so , arrhythmia (heart in the rhythm has been changes) and bradycardia (heart of size speed decrease) . in determining is used . They are different diagnostic methods with together , the situation more complete in understanding and treatment mode in choosing help will give . Exography , disease diagnosis in doing and treatment mode helps in choosing . This is basically an X-ray from the rays used without will be done and organs , teeth , neuropathologies and another pathological circumstances is described . Exography process transparent results in clear and transparent images. This is from the diagnosis after treatment mode in defining and treatment in management help Gives. Echography , systems in learning and different cases good quality the results shows . In this case , the doctor learning for right to information have will be and treatment process in optimization help gives. Echography in medicine diseases diagnosis to do _ and in treatment important diagnostic tool were ranked as Their advantages are helping doctors and patients to get complete and transparent information in understanding and diagnosing the condition.

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